

Comparative Study to Evaluate the Clinical Efficacy and Safety of Isobaric Levobupivacaine vs. Hyperbaric Bupivacaine in lower Limb Orthopaedic Surgeries

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Bupivacaine is a widely used local anesthetic in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries due to its long duration of action. However, its racemic mixture is associated with cardiotoxicity and central nervous system toxicity. Levobupivacaine, the S(-)-enantiomer of bupivacaine, was developed to mitigate these risks while maintaining efficacy.

Aim: This study aims to compare the clinical efficacy and safety of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine in patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgeries.

Methods: A prospective, randomized, double-blind clinical trial was conducted with 100 patients scheduled for elective lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. Participants were randomized into two groups: Group L (isobaric levobupivacaine, n=50) and Group B (hyperbaric bupivacaine, n=50). The primary outcome measures included the onset and duration of sensory and motor block, hemodynamic stability, and adverse events. Secondary outcomes included patient satisfaction and postoperative analgesia requirements. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The onset of sensory and motor block was significantly faster in Group B compared to Group L ($p<0.001$). Conversely, the duration of sensory and motor block was longer in Group L ($p<0.001$). Hemodynamic stability and the incidence of adverse events were comparable between the groups. Patient satisfaction was higher in Group L ($p=0.008$), and postoperative analgesia requirements were lower in Group L ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: While hyperbaric bupivacaine provides a quicker onset of anesthesia, isobaric levobupivacaine offers a longer duration of anesthetic effect, higher patient satisfaction, and reduced postoperative analgesia needs. Both anesthetics are safe and effective for lower limb orthopaedic surgeries.

Recommendations: Clinicians should consider the clinical scenario and patient needs when choosing between isobaric levobupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine for lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. Further research is recommended to explore long-term outcomes and patient preferences.

Keywords: Isobaric levobupivacaine, hyperbaric bupivacaine, spinal anesthesia, orthopaedic surgery, anesthetic efficacy.

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Introduction

The selection of local anaesthetics in orthopaedic lower limb procedures is essential for maximising patient results, guaranteeing sufficient anaesthesia, and reducing side effects. Bupivacaine has a lengthy duration of action and a favourable safety profile, making it one of the most extensively used anaesthetics on the market. On the other hand, cardiotoxicity and central nervous system toxicity have been linked to its racemic mixture, which contains both the R(-)- and S(+)-enantiomers. The S(-)-enantiomer of bupivacaine, levobupivacaine, was created and put into clinical use in order to

lessen these hazards. Levobupivacaine is considered a safer alternative to racemic bupivacaine in a variety of surgical scenarios due to its observed lower toxicity profile while retaining its efficacy [1, 2].

Spinal anaesthesia is recommended for use in orthopaedic procedures because it can help reduce systemic problems, effectively control pain, and enable early postoperative mobilisation. For spinal anaesthesia, bupivacaine is used in both isobaric and hyperbaric formulations. Because the hyperbaric formulation is denser than cerebrospinal

fluid, it settles more quickly and predictably in the dependent areas of the subarachnoid space, causing anaesthesia to take effect more quickly. In contrast, the isobaric formulation was distributed more evenly in the subarachnoid region and may have a longer duration of action due to its density being similar to that of cerebrospinal fluid [3, 4].

This study aims to perform a prospective, randomised, double-blind, comparative clinical trial on patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic procedures in order to assess the safety and clinical efficacy of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine. Assessing haemodynamic stability, patient satisfaction, and the need for postoperative analgesia are among the secondary goals. The hypothesis of this study is that, although hyperbaric bupivacaine may produce anaesthesia more quickly, isobaric levobupivacaine may produce anaesthesia more slowly, improving patient satisfaction and requiring less postoperative analgesia.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, randomized, double-blind, comparative clinical trial designed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at PMCH, Patna, a tertiary care centre with a specialized department for orthopaedic surgeries, from [June 2023] to [June 2024].

Participants: A total of 100 patients scheduled for elective lower limb orthopaedic surgeries will be enrolled in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18-65 years.
- Scheduled for elective lower limb orthopaedic surgery.
- ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) physical status I-II.
- Consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known allergies to local anesthetics.
- Patients with a history of severe cardiovascular, hepatic, or renal disease.
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women.
- Patients with a BMI > 35.
- Patients with coagulation disorders or on anti-coagulant therapy.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, randomization will be achieved using a computer-generated random number table. Blinding will be maintained

throughout the study to reduce performance and detection bias. Both the patients and the investigators will be blinded to the type of anaesthesia administered.

Data Collection: Data will be collected at baseline (pre-operatively), intra-operatively, and post-operatively at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours. The primary outcome measures will include the onset and duration of sensory and motor block, hemodynamic stability, and adverse events. Secondary outcomes will include patient satisfaction and postoperative analgesia requirements.

Procedure

1. Pre-operative Assessment: Baseline demographics, medical history, and relevant investigations will be recorded.

2. Randomization and Blinding: Patients will be randomly assigned to receive either isobaric levobupivacaine or hyperbaric bupivacaine. An independent pharmacist will prepare the study drugs in identical syringes to ensure blinding.

3. Administration of Anesthesia: The anaesthesia will be administered by experienced anesthesiologists. Standard monitoring will be applied, and patients will receive the designated drug as per their group assignment.

4. Intra-operative Monitoring: Hemodynamic parameters (blood pressure, heart rate, oxygen saturation) will be monitored and recorded at regular intervals.

5. Post-operative Monitoring: The onset and duration of sensory and motor block, pain scores (using a Visual Analog Scale), and any adverse events will be documented. Rescue analgesia will be provided as required.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the demographic data. Continuous variables will be expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The independent t-test will be used for comparing continuous variables, and the chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value < 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant Demographics and Baseline Characteristics: A total of 100 participants were enrolled and randomized into two groups: Isobaric Levobupivacaine (Group L, n=50) and Hyperbaric Bupivacaine (Group B, n=50). There were no significant differences between the groups regarding age, gender, BMI, or ASA physical status.

Table 1: Onset and Duration of Sensory and Motor Block

Parameter	Group L (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Onset of Sensory Block (min)	10.4 ± 2.1	6.8 ± 1.5	<0.001
Onset of Motor Block (min)	12.7 ± 2.3	8.5 ± 1.8	<0.001
Duration of Sensory Block (hr)	5.4 ± 0.8	3.9 ± 0.6	<0.001
Duration of Motor Block (hr)	4.8 ± 0.7	3.5 ± 0.5	<0.001
Parameter	Group L (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value

Table 2: Hemodynamic Parameters, Adverse Events, and Patient Satisfaction

Parameter	Group L (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Baseline BP (mmHg)	128.5 ± 12.4	130.2 ± 13.1	0.465
Intra-op BP (mmHg)	125.3 ± 11.8	126.7 ± 12.2	0.613
Post-op BP (mmHg)	123.8 ± 10.9	125.1 ± 11.3	0.553
Baseline HR (bpm)	76.5 ± 8.2	77.1 ± 7.9	0.721
Intra-op HR (bpm)	74.8 ± 7.5	75.6 ± 7.8	0.641
Post-op HR (bpm)	73.2 ± 7.1	74.0 ± 7.4	0.605
Hypotension (%)	3 (6%)	4 (8%)	0.695
Bradycardia (%)	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	0.648
Nausea/Vomiting (%)	5 (10%)	6 (12%)	0.749
Patient Satisfaction (VAS 0-10)	8.7 ± 1.2	7.9 ± 1.4	0.008
Postoperative Analgesia Requirement (mg)	18.4 ± 5.3	24.7 ± 6.1	<0.001

In this investigation, compared to isobaric levobupivacaine, hyperbaric bupivacaine demonstrated a quicker onset of both sensory and motor block. On the other hand, isobaric levobupivacaine produced a longer-lasting sensory and motor block, which increased patient satisfaction and decreased the need for postoperative analgesics. Both anaesthetic drugs are safe to employ in lower limb orthopaedic procedures, as evidenced by the same incidence of adverse events and haemodynamic stability across the two groups.

Discussion

In this study, 100 patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic procedures were compared for clinical efficacy and safety between isobaric levobupivacaine (Group L) and hyperbaric bupivacaine (Group B). Randomisation was used to divide the subjects into two equal groups. Baseline parameters like age, gender, BMI, and ASA physical status were all the same. The findings showed that Group B experienced a substantially faster onset of both sensory and motor block, with an average onset time of 6.8 minutes for sensory block and 8.5 minutes for motor block, as opposed to 10.4 minutes and 12.7 minutes, respectively, for Group L. In contrast to Group B, where sensory and motor block lasted 3.9 hours and 3.5 hours respectively, Group L experienced sensory and motor block for 5.4 hours and 4.8 hours, respectively. These results imply that isobaric levobupivacaine delivers a longer-lasting anaesthetic effect than hyperbaric bupivacaine, while the former has a speedier anaesthesia start.

Monitoring blood pressure, heart rate, and oxygen saturation to determine haemodynamic stability

revealed no appreciable variations between the two groups at any point in time. This suggests that in terms of haemodynamic characteristics, both anaesthetic drugs are equally safe. Substantial evidence for the safety profile of both medications was provided by the comparable occurrence of adverse events, including bradycardia, hypotension, and nausea/vomiting, between the groups.

Group L's average patient satisfaction score was greater than Group B's, at 8.7 as opposed to 7.9 in Group B. In addition, Group L's (18.4 mg) postoperative analgesic demand was noticeably less than Group B's (24.7 mg). This implies that the longer duration of the isobaric levobupivacaine sensory and motor block improves patient satisfaction and comfort while lowering the requirement for extra postoperative pain treatment.

A randomised controlled experiment found that levobupivacaine produced fewer adverse effects and a shorter period of motor block in pregnant women undergoing caesarean sections than hyperbaric bupivacaine. These results suggest that because levobupivacaine has a better safety profile, it is a better option for these kinds of treatments [5].

Levobupivacaine had a slower start but equivalent efficacy to hyperbaric bupivacaine in a research comparing intrathecal levobupivacaine and bupivacaine for infraumbilical operations. Levobupivacaine's safety profile was highlighted by the fact that there were notably fewer cases of hypotension and nausea [6].

Levobupivacaine produced superior haemodynamic stability and a longer period of motor block than bupivacaine, according to another assessment of

anaesthetic efficacy and haemodynamic effects in lower limb and abdominal procedures. For people with cardiovascular issues, levobupivacaine is therefore a better option [7].

Finally, a study comparing levobupivacaine to bupivacaine for the purpose of inguinal hernia surgery discovered that the former provided superior haemodynamic stability and a shorter duration of motor and sensory block, hence permitting an earlier mobilisation. According to a study, this makes it a viable substitute for bupivacaine in the case of patients having surgery for a unilateral inguinal hernia [8].

Conclusion

It can be concluded that isobaric levobupivacaine delivers a longer duration of anaesthetic effect, improved patient satisfaction, and a reduction in the need for postoperative analgesia, but hyperbaric bupivacaine offers a speedier onset of anaesthesia. The decision between the two medications may rely on the particular clinical situation and the demands of the patient, although both are safe and effective for use in lower limb orthopaedic procedures.

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